

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB) in Diamond Open Access Publishing

What is EDIB?

Equity, diversity, inclusion and belonging (EDIB) is a conceptual framework to support the fair treatment and full participation of all people, especially in the workplace, including populations who have historically been under-represented or subject to discrimination because of their background, identity, disability, etc.

EQUITY

Removing systemic barriers and biases to enable everyone to have equal opportunities.

DIVERSITY

Ensuring representation of diverse sexes, genders, abilities, career stages, races, ethnicities, geographic and institutional locations, linguistic and cultural backgrounds in the community

INCLUSION

Ensuring that all individuals are visible, heard, and considered

BELONGING

Treating everyone as a full member of the community and helping them to thrive

Why is EDIB important in scholarly publishing?

Open scholarly publishing seeks to make research accessible to all.

However, disparities persist in areas such as:

- Language barriers
- Gender, racial, and geographical underrepresentation
- Bias in peer review, editorial decisions, and citation practices
- Unequal access to publishing opportunities

Addressing EDIB ensures:

- A broader range of perspectives in research
- More equitable knowledge dissemination
- Increased impact and global reach of scholarly work

Different forms of discrimination (e.g. linguistic, gender, and geographical biases) can combine, overlap, or intersect. Different cultures have varying perspectives on EDIB, and legal frameworks differ across regions, making implementation complex.

Four key pillars of an EDIB strategy

Make EDIB part of core values

- Assess the needs of your research community and journal
- Identify priorities
- Acknowledge that addressing EDIB is an ongoing process in a statement

Set goals and monitor progress

- Establish specific, measurable targets
- Track progress
- Conduct EDIB audits (e.g. diversity in authorship, peer reviewers, and editorial boards).

Challenge bias in publishing

- Raise awareness about unconscious bias and provide training.
- Establish clear criteria for decision-making (e.g. by reviewers and editors)
- Promote inclusive language and citation diversity.

Develop meaningful EDIB policies

- Develop processes (e.g. double-anonymized peer review) and policies that set clear expectations for EDIB and outline consequences for engaging in non-inclusive or non-equitable practices
- Encourage journals to follow policies like Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER) Guidelines.
- Ensure accessibility features in publishing platforms for individuals with disabilities.

Resources

Resources to support the implementation of EDIB principles can be found on the European Diamond Capacity Hub.

Scan the code
to find resources

The factsheet is based on Bowker, L., Laakso, M., & Pölonen, J. (2025). Developing an Equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB) strategy for open scholarly publishing Getting started guide. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14771906>

<https://diamasproject.eu>

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